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USE OF INTERACTIVE METHODS IN TEACHING THE SCIENCE OF ENTOMOLOGY

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ANNOTATION

This article discusses innovative pedagogical technologies and ways of using them, mastering knowledge and mature skills, the role of various types of personality-oriented technologies based on the activation of students' activities and improving the efficiency of the educational process in the study of insect morphology of the subject of entomology in universities. The article is based on the idea that every activity should contribute to both the assimilation of new information and the formation of skills and processing of this information.

Key words: *Entomofauna, morphology, interactive methods, pleuritis, tergite, hemolymph, opisthognathic, ommatidia, educational technology, sternite, insect, insect pest.*

Today, the teacher faces the task of training specialists who meet the requirements of the time and improving the education system. This requires our scientists and teachers to update textbooks in the field of education, taking into account the requirements of modernity, the introduction of innovative and pedagogical technologies in the educational process. Therefore, the role and importance of modern interactive methods and innovative technologies in the education process is very

important. Pedagogical technologies and their application ensure the availability of assimilation of knowledge and mature skills. It should be noted that at the moment, the role of various types of personality-oriented technologies based on the activation of students' activities and improving the efficiency of the educational process has sharply increased, which involve the use of various forms and methods of organizing educational activities, allow to reveal the subjective potential of both the student and the teacher. These are, first of all, the use of active learning methods, dialogical forms of organizing seminars, elements of heuristics, the synectic method, mini-conferences and group discussions, educational simulation and business games, elements of psychological training, master classes, group and independent work, and much more. Innovative learning, as a process and result of educational and official activities, is focused on the formation of a person's readiness for dynamic changes in society, through the development of creativity. One of such innovative technologies is modular training. The methodology of the modular system is based on the idea that every activity should contribute to both the assimilation of new information and the formation of skills and processing of this Sirtqi bo'lim "Aniq va tabiiy fanlar kafedrası"da xalqaro konferensiya 180 information. Thus, it is logical to use a block (modular) organization of the material supply. Namely: lecture (lesson of learning new material), seminar, research, independent work (lessons of improving knowledge, skills, skills), colloquium, (control lessons – intermediate control, lessons of accounting and evaluation of knowledge and skills, final control). Innovative technologies are not only a pedagogical approach to teaching a particular topic, but also innovations and changes in the activities of teachers and students, in the implementation of which interactive methods are mainly used. Interactive teaching methods are a special form of organization of cognitive activity, in which students in the learning process have the opportunity to understand and think about what they know and think and want to learn. The role of the teacher in interactive lessons partially leads to the orientation of students' activities to achieve the goals of the lesson. The use of pedagogical technologies in all areas of higher education, including problem-based learning;

technologies that develop critical thinking; modular technologies; collaboration technologies; differentiated and individual learning technology. [1] Of the above innovative technologies, I consider it expedient to use several technologies for effective teaching of the subject of entomology. The advantages of this application are as follows. For example, when studying the topic “Morphology of insects”, the teacher gives a lecture on the topic using IT presentations as a visual aid. During the explanation of new material, special attention is paid to important points that need to be paid attention to. To consolidate the material, you can use work in groups or individually on cards, a blitz survey, a cluster, etc. Performing a practical task, students not only learn new material, but also the skills to use new knowledge. [1,4] The use of innovative technologies in the educational process increases the effectiveness of training. When creating educational technologies for disciplines, it is advisable to proceed from diversity, creativity, non-standard approaches, taking into account the specifics and patterns of each discipline. In this process, it is advisable to take into account the specifics of subjects, forms of education and topics. [2,3] Sometimes the middle eye disappears, and only two lateral ones remain, less often the disappearance of paired ones is observed while maintaining the middle eye. As a rule, eyes are found in adult, well-flying insects, but they are absent in many lepidoptera and diptera and are found in the larvae of mayfly dragonflies.

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